

FLYROCK EVALUATION TO REDUCE SAFE DISTANCE FROM 500M TO 300M AT PT. VALE INDONESIA, SOROWAKO, SOUTH SULAWESI, INDONESIA

¹Harry Subekti, ²Haris Handayana

Dept. Technical Services and Quality Control

PT. Hanwha Mining Services Indonesia, Job Site Sorowako, PT Vale Indonesia

¹E-mail : harry.subekti@hmsi.co.id ²E-mail : haris.handayana@hmsi.co.id

ABSTRACT

Flyrock fragmentation is a rock or rocks that throwing by blasting. Rock fragments thrown beyond the safe radius can cause damage to mechanical tools. This study aims to determine the safe distance from flyrock result from blasting at the company and the factors that affect the flyrock distance. This study uses survey methods and quantitative analysis with calculations also analysis of theoretical flyrock distance predictions from the blast. Data collection at PT. Vale Indonesia uses Leica GS 14 and cameras to observe blasting activities. PT. Vale Indonesia run the project of mining process at Sorowako , Nuha sub-district, South Sulawesi Province. Field observation conducted and found that PT. Vale Indonesia stated for safe distance all heavy equipment and human are in 500m due to the incident that occurred in last decade, to change the safe distance for heavy equipment back to 300m, a technical study is needed as well as determining the value of the safety factor for throwing flyrock in every blasting activity carried out. Determination of the estimated maximum flyrock throwing distance using two methods namely the empirical method and the dimensional analysis method, the study is done in order to obtain accurate and precise results in accordance with the conditions of the blasting location. The empirical method used is based on Lundborg theory (1981) and, Richard and Moore (2005), while the dimensional analysis method is based on the theory of Ebrahim Ghasemi (2012). By using the dimensional analysis method from Ebrahim Ghasemi (2012) the deviation from actual flyrock throw is 38.1%, and with Richard Moore's empirical method with a deviation value of 70.5%. From these results, it is known that the method produces an estimate of the flyrock-throwing distance that is closest to the actual flyrock-throwing distance is the dimensional analysis method with a difference of 6 m with a safety factor value of 1.5, based on the dimensional analysis method, a trial was carried out to see the appropriate safe radius, to determine the current safe radius at Quarry PT. Vale Indonesia is appropriate or can be reduced.

Kata kunci :Flyrock, radius aman, stemming

I. INTRODUCTION

Quarry mining activities are carried out by PT. Vale Indonesia, cannot be separated from the hard nature of the rock so that in practice some can be excavated directly by mechanical means and some can only be excavated after blasting. The blasting method is a very effective method for breaking rocks in general which cannot be done directly by mechanical means, impact to the environment from blasting activities is the presence of flyrock

Flyrock is rock fragmentation that is thrown beyond the safe limit radius which can cause damage to

infrastructure, damage to mechanical equipment, injury, and even death to humans. Flyrock became one of the main concerns in every blasting (Havis, et al. 2015). Flyrock causes heavy equipment to move a considerable distance and requires time to move to a safe radius, this has a very negative impact on mining activities due to loss of production due to delays in moving equipment. In addition, flyrock is very dangerous for workers and shotfirer who are near the blasting area. Therefore, it is necessary to study the Flyrock at PT. Vale Indonesia Sorowako to reduce the safety distance of the heavy equipment from 500m to 300m based on the maximum distance from flyrock-throwing caused by blasting and the key to this technical study is not only to increase

productivity but also to ensure the safety level from the dangers of flyrock.

II. GEOLOGY

The parent rock of nickel ore is peridotite. According to **Vinogradov**, the average ultra-alkaline rock has a nickel content of 0.2%, nickel element is present in the crystal lattice of olivine and pyroxene minerals, as a result of the substitution of Fe and Mg atoms. Process of substitution between Ni, Fe, and Mg can be explained because the ion radius and ionic charge are almost the same between these elements, serpentinization process that occurs in peridotite rocks due to the influence of hydrothermal solutions will change peridotite rocks into serpentinite rocks or perodite serpentinite rocks. Meanwhile, the chemical and physical processes of air, water, and continuous hot-cold changes cause disintegration and decomposition of the source rock.

Chemical weathering in particular, CO₂-rich groundwater from the air and plant decay decompose unstable minerals (olivine and pyroxene) in ultra-alkaline rocks, producing soluble Mg, Fe, Ni, Si tends to form colloids of very fine silica particles. In solution, Fe is oxidized and precipitates as ferric hydroxide, eventually forming minerals such as goethite, limonite, and haematite near the surface, with these minerals, elemental cobalt is always included in small amounts.

Solutions containing Mg, Ni, and Si continuously as long as the solution is acidic, until a condition where the atmosphere is quite neutral due to contact with soil and rock, there is a tendency to form hydrosilicate deposits. The nickel contained in the silicate or hydrosilicate chains with compositions that may vary will settle in cracks or fractures known as garnierite and chrysoprase veins. While the residual solution will form a compound called saprolite which is yellow-brown in color. Other elements such as Ca and Mg dissolved as bicarbonate will be carried down to the weathering limit and will be deposited as dolomite, magnesite which usually fills cracks or fractures in the source rock. In the field, these veins are known as the clue boundary between the weathering zone and the fresh rock zone, which is known as weathering roots.

The bedrock is the lowest part of the laterite profile. Composed of boulders larger than 75 cm and

peridotite blocks (bedrock) and generally do not contain economic minerals (metal content is close to or equal to bedrock). The bedrock is the origin of laterite nickel which is generally an ultramafic igneous rock, namely harzburgite and dunite which in the fracture has been filled with 5-10% iron oxide, minor garnierite and > 35% silica. Permeability of bedrock increases in proportion to the intensity of serpentinization. This zone is strongly fractured, sometimes open, filled with garnierite and silica minerals. This fracture is thought to be the cause of the root zone, namely the high-grade Ni zone, but it is hidden. (Wikipedia, 2021)

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted at the Quarry PT. Vale Indonesia from April 2021 to July 2021. The measurement of the maximum flyrock throw was carried out 41 times, and the analysis of this observation used a Leica GS 14 GPS as a radius reference for determining the maximum flyrock throw. The calculation of the distance of the flyrock throw was carried out at the Quarry PT. Vale Indonesia Sorowako and Petea carried out theoretically and actually oriented to the distance between spacing, burden, minimum stemming height, minimum hole depth, powder factor, and average of charge mass. The empirical method is based on the theory of Richard and Moore (2005), and Lundborg (1981), while the dimensional analysis method is based on the theory of Ebrahim Ghasemi (2012).

According to the tests carried out by Richard and Moore (2005), there are 3 main factors that influence the occurrence of flyrock in blasting activities, namely, Face Burst occurs when the distance of the burden on the front row of blasting in the field which is sometimes too close can cause potential flyrock.

Fig 1. Flyrock mechanism (Richard and Moore, 2005)

Face Burst

This phenomenon occurs when explosive charges are in adjacent of the major geological structures or zones of the high-pressure gases of the explosives jet along the weakness zones (paths of low resistance) and generate noise, air blast, and flyrock

$$L = \frac{k^2}{g} \left(\frac{\sqrt{m}}{B} \right)^{2,6}$$

L = Horizontal Throw (m)

k = Site Constant

g = Gravitational Constant (9,8 m/s²)

m = Mass Charge per meter (kg/m)

B = Burden (m)

Cratering

The stemming region of a blast pattern usually contains a weakened layer due to previous blasting from the bench above. In this region, blast gases easily jet into the air and propagate cracks. The venting gases through this region produce cratering and flyrock events. This is particularly significant if insufficient stemming is used. Similar effects can result if short inter-row delays are applied. These gases will produce excessive air blast and flyrock. Cratering effect is also happened if blasting rows are incorrectly initiated (initiating back rows earlier than front rows)

$$L = \frac{k^2}{g} \left(\frac{\sqrt{m}}{SH} \right)^{2,6}$$

L = Horizontal Throw (m)

k = Site Constant

g = Gravitational Constant (9,8 m/s²)

m = Mass Charge per meter (kg/m)

SH = Stemming Height (m)

Rifling

This event occurs when stemming material is insufficient. Blast gases can stream up the blast hole along the path of least resistance resulting in stemming ejection and sometimes ejection of the collar rock as harmful flyrock. The stemming column should contain individual rocks that are of disproportionate size to the blast hole diameter, these can become lethal projectiles. This mechanism of flyrock manifestation is closely related to the stemming release pulse for air blast.

$$L = \frac{k^2}{g} \left(\frac{\sqrt{m}}{SH} \right)^{2,6} \sin 2\theta$$

L = Horizontal Throw (m)

k = Site Constant

g = Gravitational Constant (9,8 m/s²)

m = Mass Charge per meter (kg/m)

SH = Stemming Height (m)

θ = Blast Hole angle

Lundborg (1981)

Developed an empirical calculation equation to predict the maximum throw of a flyrock

$$L = 143 d (q - 0,2)$$

L = maximum trajectory (m)

d = Blast hole diameter (mm)

q = specific charge (kg/m³)

Ebrahim Ghasemi (2012)

make an equation to predict the flyrock distance using a dimensional analysis method based on blasting parameters that can be controlled.

Fd = f (B-1.336 S 1.201 St-2.196 H 0.347D -0.201 (P/Q) -0.171)

Fd = flyrock distance (m),

B = Burden (m)

S = Spacing (m)

St = Stemming (m),

H = Hole Depth (m)

P = Powder factor

Q = Mean Charge per blast hole (Kg)

Factor of Safety (FOS)

The factor of safety (FoS), also known as (and used interchangeably with) safety factor (SF), expresses how much stronger a system is than it needs to be for an intended load. Safety factors are often calculated using detailed analysis because comprehensive testing is impractical on many projects. FOS are the numbers to determine the value of safety and accuracy of a theoretical calculation. The FOS value <1 above means that the calculation of the flyrock analysis of the explosion to be carried out is not feasible, basically FOS can be inputted with the number 1 and a maximum of 2

$$\text{FOS} = \frac{\text{Distance to point of concern}}{\text{Max potential flyrock projection}}$$

IV. DATA AND ANALYSIS

From the measurement data of distance between spaces, distance between loads, minimum stemming height, minimum hole depth, powder factor, average hole charge and burden distance, obtained which has the highest regression value to the distance of the

flyrock throw with $R^2 = 0.026$ for burden and space. From 41 observations of actual flyrock throws at the Sorowako and Petea Quarry, none of the flyrocks are thrown more than 300 m from the blasting area. The average maximum flyrock throw during the observation is 17 m and the farthest is 50 m.

Table 1. Flyrock actual collected at PT.Vale Indonesia

Date	Locations	Holes Number	Burden	Space	DL	Average Depth	Average Stemming	Flyrock Throwing Actual
6-Apr-21	Tonia Terry	50	5	5	0.216	7.42	3.73	25 m
7-Apr-21	Lembo Quarry	46	5	5	0.23	10.1	4.6	10 m
8-Apr-21	Tonia Terry	50	5	5	0.23	8.84	4.23	15 m
13-Apr-21	Tonia Terry	50	5	5	0.22	8.43	2.6	15 m
15-Apr-21	Lembo Quarry	50	5	5	0.23	9.2	3.1	5 m
19-Apr-21	Petea	50	6	6	0.17	9.2	4	30 m
20-Apr-21	Tonia Terry	50	5	5	0.22	8.89	4.39	5 m
21-Apr-21	Lembo Quarry	50	5	5	0.21	7.92	4.05	11 m
22-Apr-21	Watulabu	50	5	5	0.19	5.7	3.26	5 m
26-Apr-21	Lembo Quarry	70	5	5	0.21	8.17	4.1	5 m
27-Apr-21	Tonia Terry	50	5	5	0.21	8.18	4.13	5 m
29-Apr-21	Anoa N	90	5	5	0.22	9.55	4.6	7 m
3-May-21	Petea D2C2	30	6	6	0.15	8.86	4.4	10 m
4-May-21	Petea D2C2	70	6	6	0.15	8.62	4.2	20 m
6-May-21	Petea B0C6	50	6	6	0.22	9.73	4.38	30 m
7-May-21	Konde South	40	5	5	0.22	9.7	4.7	6 m
10-May-21	Nickel Hill	80	5	5	0.19	8.88	4.86	7 m
11-May-21	Konde south	50	5	5	0.23	8.66	3.94	20 m
18-May-21	Tonia Terry	66	5	5	0.21	8.33	4.15	25 m
19-May-21	Petea B0C6	30	6	6	0.14	7.02	3.8	10 m
20-May-21	Nickel hill	36	5	5	0.22	9	4.41	13 m
25-May-21	Anoa N	60	5	5	0.22	8.59	4.2	15 m
31-May-21	Lembo Quarry	50	5	5	0.21	8.19	4.12	15 m
3-Jun-21	Lembo Quarry	50	5	5	0.25	7.6	3.41	15 m
7-Jun-21	Petea D2C2	30	6	6	0.17	11.67	5	10 m
8-Jun-21	Tonia Terry	50	5	5	0.22	8.48	4.23	25 m
9-Jun-21	Lembo Quarry	52	5	5	0.23	8.3	4.18	10 m
11-Jun-21	Tonia Terry (PJU)	70	5	5	0.2	7.07	3.73	15 m
14-Jun-21	Petea D2C2	50	6	6	0.15	9.33	4.5	10 m
15-Jun-21	Tonia Terry	54	5	5	0.21	8.07	4.1	15 m
17-Jun-21	Petea B1C2	60	6	6	0.16	10.08	4.78	50 m
21-Jun-21	Lembo Quarry	50	5	5	0.24	8.16	3.67	50 m
22-Jun-21	Tonia Terry	54	5	5	0.24	8.54	3.84	30 m
23-Jun-21	Petea B1C2	50	6	6	0.15	8.73	4.34	20 m
25-Jun-21	Tonia Terry	50	5	5	0.19	7.21	4.5	10 m
29-Jun-21	Tonia Terry	50	5	5	0.21	8.11	4.12	20 m
1-Jul-21	Lembo Quarry	50	5	5	0.22	8.4	4.17	30 m
2-Jul-21	Watulabu	50	5	5	0.31	9.94	5.38	20 m
6-Jul-21	Petea D3C2	50	6	6	0.14	7.95	4.1	15 m
8-Jul-21	Lembo Quarry	50	5	5	0.22	7.32	3.9	20 m
13-Jul-21	Tonia Terry	50	5	5	0.22	9	4.5	25 m
14-Jul-21	Petea D2C2	72	6	6	0.18	8.72	4.3	10 m

The results of the calculation of the standard deviation between the predicted maximum flyrock throw and the actual maximum flyrock throw, the results show that the predicted maximum flyrock throw and the actual maximum flyrock throw in Richard and Moore's theory in the face burst formula is 11,9 m and in the cratering formula is 39,2 m, and in Ebrahim Ghasemi's theory is 6,4 m.

Table 2. Deviation Value

Actual Flyrock	Deviation (m)	Deviation (%)
Lundborg	-8.47	-50.2%
Gasemi, E	6.4 m	38.1%
Face Burst	11.9 m	70.5%
Cratering	39.2 m	69.9%

Lundborg's theory has a negative value because the calculation parameters are only limited to the diameter of the hole and the amount of explosive stuffing

in one hole so that it does not make a major contribution to the cause of fly rock, so it is not included as a reference in determining the prediction of fly rock-throwing in blasting. From the relative deviation value, it can be seen that the dimensional analysis theory of Ebrahim Ghasemi is the closest to the actual maximum throw.

Fig 2. Flyrock distribution after the blast on map

Fig 3. 3D view of flyrock distribution after the blast on map

Fig 4. Chart for flyrock throwing frequency

Safety factor on fly rock for PT. Vale Indonesia used is 1.5 which allows heavy equipment to move as far as 300 m from the blasting location and from the results of data collection in the field and compared to the predicted maximum fly rock throw at 200 m.

Table 3. Flyrock actual and prediction

Date	Locations	Flyrock Throwing Actual	Flyrock Throwing Theoretical (Lundborg)	Flyrock Throwing Theoretical (Ebrahim Ghasemi)	Flyrock Throwing		Safety Factor 1 - 3
					Face Burst	Cratering	
6-Apr-21	Tonia Terry	25 m	9 m	27.8 m	31.9 m	68.4 m	1.5 m
7-Apr-21	Lembo Quarry	10 m	8 m	18.4 m	31.9 m	39.7 m	1.5 m
8-Apr-21	Tonia Terry	15 m	8 m	21.8 m	31.9 m	49.3 m	1.5 m
13-Apr-21	Tonia Terry	15 m	8 m	63.0 m	31.9 m	174.9 m	1.5 m
15-Apr-21	Lembo Quarry	5 m	8 m	43.6 m	31.9 m	110.7 m	1.5 m
19-Apr-21	Petea	30 m	8 m	22.7 m	19.9 m	57.1 m	1.5 m
20-Apr-21	Tonia Terry	5 m	8 m	20.1 m	31.9 m	44.8 m	1.5 m
21-Apr-21	Lembo Quarry	11 m	9 m	23.4 m	31.9 m	55.2 m	1.5 m
22-Apr-21	Watulabu	5 m	9 m	35.9 m	31.9 m	97.1 m	1.5 m
26-Apr-21	Lembo Quarry	5 m	9 m	22.8 m	31.9 m	53.5 m	1.5 m
27-Apr-21	Tonia Terry	5 m	9 m	22.5 m	31.9 m	52.5 m	1.5 m
29-Apr-21	Anoa N	7 m	8 m	18.3 m	31.9 m	39.7 m	1.5 m
3-May-21	Petea DZC2	10 m	8 m	18.3 m	19.9 m	44.5 m	1.5 m
4-May-21	Petea DZC2	20 m	8 m	20.0 m	19.9 m	50.3 m	1.5 m
6-May-21	Petea BOC6	30 m	8 m	19.9 m	19.9 m	45.1 m	1.5 m
7-May-21	Konde South	6 m	8 m	17.5 m	31.9 m	37.5 m	1.5 m
10-May-21	Nickel Hill	7 m	8 m	15.9 m	31.9 m	34.4 m	1.5 m
11-May-21	Konde south	20 m	8 m	25.5 m	31.9 m	59.3 m	1.5 m
18-May-21	Tonia Terry	25 m	8 m	21.6 m	31.9 m	51.8 m	1.5 m
19-May-21	Petea BOC6	10 m	8 m	23.2 m	19.9 m	65.2 m	1.5 m
20-May-21	Nickel hill	13 m	8 m	19.8 m	31.9 m	44.3 m	1.5 m
25-May-21	Anoa N	15 m	8 m	22.0 m	31.9 m	50.3 m	1.5 m
31-May-21	Lembo Quarry	15 m	9 m	22.6 m	31.9 m	52.8 m	1.5 m
3-Jun-21	Lembo Quarry	15 m	8 m	34.3 m	31.9 m	86.4 m	1.5 m
7-Jun-21	Petea DZC2	10 m	8 m	14.5 m	19.9 m	31.9 m	1.5 m
8-Jun-21	Tonia Terry	25 m	8 m	21.6 m	31.9 m	49.3 m	1.5 m
9-Jun-21	Lembo Quarry	10 m	9 m	22.4 m	31.9 m	50.9 m	1.5 m
11-Jun-21	Tonia Terry (PIU)	15 m	9 m	27.4 m	31.9 m	68.4 m	1.5 m
14-Jun-21	Petea DZC2	10 m	8 m	17.5 m	19.9 m	42.0 m	1.5 m
15-Jun-21	Tonia Terry	15 m	9 m	22.8 m	31.9 m	53.5 m	1.5 m
17-Jun-21	Petea B1C2	50 m	8 m	15.6 m	19.9 m	35.9 m	1.5 m
21-Jun-21	Lembo Quarry	50 m	8 m	29.4 m	31.9 m	71.4 m	1.5 m
22-Jun-21	Tonia Terry	30 m	8 m	27.0 m	31.9 m	63.4 m	1.5 m
23-Jun-21	Petea B1C2	20 m	8 m	18.5 m	19.9 m	46.2 m	1.5 m
25-Jun-21	Tonia Terry	10 m	9 m	18.3 m	31.9 m	42.0 m	1.5 m
29-Jun-21	Tonia Terry	20 m	9 m	22.6 m	31.9 m	52.8 m	1.5 m
1-Jul-21	Lembo Quarry	30 m	8 m	22.2 m	31.9 m	51.2 m	1.5 m
2-Jul-21	Watulabu	20 m	8 m	14.1 m	31.9 m	26.4 m	1.5 m
6-Jul-21	Petea D3C2	15 m	9 m	20.8 m	19.9 m	53.5 m	1.5 m
8-Jul-21	Lembo Quarry	20 m	8 m	24.3 m	31.9 m	60.9 m	1.5 m
13-Jul-21	Tonia Terry	25 m	8 m	19.1 m	31.9 m	42.0 m	1.5 m
14-Jul-21	Petea DZC2	10 m	8 m	19.8 m	19.9 m	47.3 m	1.5 m

V. CONCLUSION

1. Prediction of the maximum throw distance for fly rock at the blasting location, using the dimensional analysis method based on the Ebrahim Ghasemi tori because it has a relative error of 38.1% and a deviation of 6.4 meters.
2. Based on actual data in the field, it is found that the farthest flyrock throw is 50 m.
3. The safety factor based on the calculation of the safe distance for the heavy equipment can be 1.5 due to the data actual and predictions showed that no flying

rocks are thrown more than 300m from the blast area. Thus the standard safety radius for heavy equipment can be reduced from 500 m to 300 m.

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